

TÜBİTAK

**TUBITAK 2209-A UNIVERSITY STUDENTS
RESEARCH PROJECT SUPPORT PROGRAM**

**MOBILE APPLICATION FOR HEARING IMPAIRED INDIVIDUALS TO
COMMUNICATE IN DAILY LIFE**

KARABUK UNIVERSITY

COMPUTER ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

PROJECT THEMATIC AREA

Digital Transformation in Communication

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1. SUMMARY

Deaf individuals experience serious difficulties in their daily lives due to speech or hearing loss. According to World Health Organization data, there are approximately 466 million deaf people in the world. This number is projected to reach 900 million by 2050 [1]. In Turkey, this number is approximately 3 million. People with hearing or speech impairments use sign language to communicate with each other. However, most people around them in their daily lives do not know sign language. This makes their daily lives quite difficult. Despite the advancement of technology in the 21st century, there has been no transformation to minimize the difficulties in the lives of individuals with hearing or speech impairments. The main goal of this project is to make it easier for individuals with hearing or speech impairments and the people around them to communicate with each other. This will allow those around hearing-impaired individuals to express themselves. As a result, hearing-impaired individuals will no longer be isolated from daily life.

2. ORIGINAL VALUE

2.1. Importance of the Topic

The project to be developed will establish an algorithm between spoken language and sign language to enable hearing-impaired individuals to communicate with others in their daily lives. It will be an important study because it will be able to perform instant translation with the help of various add-ons and will make a significant contribution to the daily lives of hearing-impaired individuals in this area.

2.2. Original Value of the Research Proposal

There are very few mobile applications in the literature that translate spoken language into sign language. The existing applications are generally developed in local languages specific to their respective communities. Furthermore, various deficiencies have been observed in the testing phase of such applications developed to date. For example, these applications real-time translation and

resulting in observed performance deficiencies [2]. Research indicates that tissue compatibility is particularly low and costs are high [3]. Additionally, there are significant flaws in the database system to be used, the programming language in which the mobile application will be coded, and the animation dimensions [4]. Various fast plugins and small-sized animation tools will be used to solve these flaws. The conversion of perceived sound into sign language with Turkish language support creates unique values in this field in terms of the programming language and tools used.

2.3. Research Question/Hypothesis

- What is the response time in the process of converting perceived sound into sign language through animation?
- If hearing-impaired individuals could communicate better, would their roles in society increase?
- If this communication gap were eliminated, would the expectations and satisfaction of hearing-impaired individuals in life increase?
- If people without disabilities could communicate with hearing-impaired individuals without needing to know sign language, would they be reluctant to communicate with hearing-impaired individuals, or would this reluctance decrease?

2.4. Objectives and Goals

A one-way communication application will be designed to enable individuals with hearing or speech impairments to communicate with people who do not know sign language in their daily lives. In this application, the voice transmitted by the person will be instantly translated into sign language. This will facilitate communication between the hearing-impaired individual and the people around them.

The goal is to enable individuals with hearing impairments to communicate easily with the community they live in, minimize the problems they encounter in their daily lives, and increase their expectations and satisfaction with life.

3. METHOD

Initially, an animated character obtained from the Unity Asset Store will be edited using the Blender 3D drawing program. This character will be designed to display hand and finger movements. There are 3D animations that speak sign language and prepared sign language dictionaries in the literature [5]. This character prepared in the Blender program will be transferred to the Unity game engine, and sign language animations will be applied to the character.

The 'Speech to Text' asset available in the Unity game engine will be used to make the character move according to the sound received from the user [6]. Subsequently, the sound received from the user will be converted into text, and the words will be associated with the sign language data in the database.

The algorithms used in the character design phase will be tested for speed and accuracy, and if necessary, different algorithms will be used for measurement. The sign language dictionary prepared by experts from the Ministry of Family and Social Services will be used to transfer sign language to the character [7].

3.1. Data Adjustment

The sign language dictionary contains the 2000 most frequently used words/concepts and 29 letters [7]. In the project, each movement of the animated character will be associated with this data and the animation recordings will be transferred to the database. It will be ensured that the data is instantly transferred to the user from the database.

3.2. Segmentation Phase

The architectural structure shown in the figure summarizes the application. First, the sound is converted into words using the Speech to Text plugin. Then, this text is associated with the sign language data in the database and transferred to the animation character.

Figure 1 - Working Architecture Converting Perceived Sound into Sign Language [8]

3.3. Sign Language and Animation Association

This image shows the association of the converted text with animations after the detected sound is converted to text. First, the detected sound is converted to text, then it is associated with the appropriate animations in the database. As a result, the detected similar sounds and associated animations are displayed on the screen.

Figure 2 - Sample Animation Converting Perceived Sound into Sign Language [9]

4. PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Karabuk University – TÜBİTAK 2209-A Research Project Gantt Chart (Scaled to Deadline)

4.2. Risk Management

RISK MANAGEMENT TABLE

NO	Most Significant Risks	Risk Management (Plan B)
1	Within the scope of our project the data to be used may be corrupted or lost.	To prevent this situation, backups of the data to be used will be created and stored not only locally but also in the cloud.
2	Performance issues may arise during real-time translation. issues may occur.	Various fast plugins and small-sized animation tools will be provided to address these issues.
3	There may not always be an environment suitable for voice communication.	The application will be designed to allow translation using both voice and text.
4	The application size may be large due to the large amount of data.	Small animations will be used.
5	Users may use different mobile devices with different operating systems.	The application will be designed to be compatible with multiple platforms.

5. WIDESPREAD IMPACT

TABLE OF EXPECTED WIDESPREAD IMPACT FROM THE RESEARCH PROPOSAL

Types of Widespread Impact	Expected Output, Results, and Impacts from the Proposed Research
<p>Scientific/Academic (Article, Presentation, Book Chapter, Book)</p>	<p>We aim to enable school staff and students to communicate more comfortably in special schools for the hearing impaired.</p>
<p>Economic/Commercial/Social (Product, Prototype, Patent, Utility Model, Production License, Variety Registration, Spin-off/Start-up Company, Visual/Auditory Archive, Inventory/Database/Documentation Production, Copyrighted Work, Media Coverage, Fair, Project Market, Workshop, Training, etc. Scientific Event, Institution/Organization that will use the Project Results, etc. other common effects)</p>	<p>The target audience of this project is hearing-impaired individuals and those who communicate with them. Through the project we will develop, we aim to enable hearing-impaired individuals to play a more active role in their daily lives in terms of health, education, work, and social life. In this way, we aim to increase the psychological self-confidence of hearing-impaired individuals and improve their quality of life.</p>
<p>Researcher Training and New Project(s) Creation (Bachelor's Bachelor's/Doctoral Thesis, National/International New Project)</p>	<p>As a result of this project, the lack of Turkish sources has been addressed, and it will serve as a useful reference for future ideas related to this project.</p>

6 SCREENSHOTS

Example 1 - Login Screen

Example 2 - Work Example 1

Example 3 - Work Example 2

Example 4 - Work Example 3

7. REFERENCES

[1] “World Hearing Day Infographic”, WHO, 2018.

<https://www.who.int/deafness/world-hearing-day/World-Hearing-Day-Infographic-EN.pdf>

[2] “Unity Academic Alliance”, Unity Technologies,

2021. <https://unity.com/products/unity-academic-alliance>

[3] Bora ÖZTEKİN, Nadire ÇAVUŞ, “Development of a Sign Recognition System for Individuals with Hearing and Speech Disabilities”, Dergi Park Akademik, 2019.

<https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/fe/issue/48876/619914>

[4] Teemu Laine, Joonas Westlin, Sung Lae Kim, Hae Jung Suk, Jeong Hwa Kang, Jun Mo Jung,

"Using Unity 3D to Facilitate Mobile Augmented Reality Game Development," IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things, 2014.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271462295_Using_Unity_3D_to_facilitate_mobile_augmented_reality_game_development

[5] "ITU Sign Language Speaking Animation Video," ITU,

2017. <https://web.itu.edu.tr/tid/videos.html>

[6] “Speech Recognition System- Unity”, Stendhal Syndrome Studio, Unity Asset Store,

2020. <https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/tools/audio/speech-recognition-system-187171>

[7] “Current Turkish Sign Language Dictionary”, Ministry of Family and

Social Services, 2021. <http://tidsozluk.net/>

[8] Debashis Das Chakladar, Pradeep Kumar, Shubham Mandal, Partha Pratim Roy, Masakazu Iwamura Byung-Gyu Kim, “3D Avatar Approach for Continuous Sign Movement Using Speech/Text”, 2021.

<https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/11/8/3439/htm>

[9] Şafak Bayır, "An Examination of Turkish Sign Language: Communication and Linguistics," Journal of the National Academy of Education, 2018.

<https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/565148>